

Research Article

Development and Validation of RP-HPLC Method for Estimation of Sofosbuvir in Bulk Drug and Dosage Form

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ABSTRACT

Sofosbuvir is an antiviral medication used to treat hepatitis C (HCV) infection. It is a nucleotide analog that inhibits the HCV RNA polymerase, preventing the virus from replicating. Sofosbuvir is typically used in combination with other antiviral drugs and is administered orally. A novel, accurate, and robust reverse-phase high-performance liquid chromatography (RP-HPLC) method was developed and validated for the quantitative estimation of Sofosbuvir in bulk drug and Dosage formulations. In developed RP-HPLC method, the analyte were resolved by using isocratic program and mobile phase was used Methanol Water (75:25 % v/v) at a flow rate of 1.0ml/min, on HPLC system containing UV- visible detector with Openlab EZ- Chrome Software and Kromasil C18, 250 mm X 4.6 mm, 5 μ m. The detection was carried out at 261 nm. The results of analysis in the developed method were validated in terms of linearity, accuracy, precision, robustness, limit of detection and limit of quantification. The developed method has several advantages, including reproducibility of results. rapid analysis, simple sample preparation and improved selectivity as well as sensitivity. The regression coefficient (r^2) for each analyte is not less than 0.999 which shows good linearity. The % recovery was in the acceptable range in tablet dosage form. The %RSD was also less than 2% showing high degree of precision of the proposed method.

INTRODUCTION

Sofosbuvir is an oral nucleoside analogue and potent inhibitor of the hepatitis C virus (HCV) RNA polymerase that is used in combination with other antiviral agents to treat chronic hepatitis C.

Elevations in serum enzyme levels during sofosbuvir therapy are uncommon, and it has not been implicated convincingly in cases of clinically apparent liver injury with jaundice. Nevertheless, and for unknown reasons, successful antiviral therapy of hepatitis C with sofosbuvir and other

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direct acting agents in patients with cirrhosis is occasionally complicated by hepatic decompensation; furthermore, treatment can cause reactivation of hepatitis B in susceptible patients coinfecting with the hepatitis B virus (HBV) [1].

Sofosbuvir (soe fos' bue vir) is an orally available nucleotide analogue that has potent activity against the RNA-dependent RNA polymerase of the hepatitis C virus (HCV). Sofosbuvir is a monophosphorylated uracil derivative whose single phosphate is protected by an alaninate cap that allows for the absorption and uptake of the molecule by hepatocytes where it is hydrolyzed to sofosbuvir monophosphate. Intracellular host kinases then convert it to the active triphosphate moiety. In multiple clinical trials, sofosbuvir has been shown to cause a rapid and marked decline in serum HCV RNA levels and, in combination with other antiviral agents and with more prolonged therapy, to result in sustained clearance of HCV (sustained virological response: SVR) in a high proportion of patients. Sofosbuvir was approved for use in the United States in 2013 to be used in combination with ribavirin or with both peginterferon and ribavirin in patients with chronic hepatitis C, genotypes 1, 2, 3 or 4. Sofosbuvir is available in tablets of 400 mg under the brand name Solvaldi, the recommended dose being 400 mg once daily in combination with either ribavirin alone (1000 or 1200 mg daily for 12 weeks for genotype 2 and 24 weeks for genotype 3) or in combination with both ribavirin and peginterferon for 12 weeks for patients with genotype 1. Subsequently, a fixed combination of sofosbuvir (400 mg) and the HCV NS5A replication complex inhibitor ledipasvir (le dip' as vir: 90 mg) was approved for use in patients with chronic hepatitis C, genotype 1 in 2014 and for genotype 4 in 2015. This combination is available as a fixed dose, single tablet under the brand name Harvoni and the recommended dose is one tablet daily for 12

weeks, which can be shortened to 8 weeks in selected patients [2,3].

In addition, sofosbuvir combined with NS5A inhibitors with broader activity against HCV genotypes, daclatasvir (dak lat' as vir: 2015) and velpatasvir (vel pat' as vir: 2016), has been shown to be effective in treating almost all HCV genotypes with sustained response rates of 95% or greater in response to 12 weeks of treatment in genotypes 1, 2, 4, 5 and 6. In 2016, the fixed combination of sofosbuvir (400 mg) and velpatasvir (100 mg) was approved for use in patients with all 6 genotypes of hepatitis C. This combination is available as a fixed dose, single tablet under the brand name Epclusa. The recommended dose is one tablet daily for 12 weeks. For patients with decompensated cirrhosis (Childs-Pugh Class B or C), ribavirin (1000 to 1200 mg in two divided doses daily) should be added to Epclusa for 12 weeks. Finally, the combination of sofosbuvir with an HCV specific NS3/4 protease inhibitor [2014] was also shown to be highly effective in patients with genotype 1 infection generally in 12 week courses [4,5].

For patients who fail to respond to a two or three drug combination of direct acting antiviral agents, combinations of potent agents active against the three major HCV polypeptide products have been developed and have shown excellent activity in these refractory patients. The first such regimen was a single tablet formulation of sofosbuvir (400 mg), velpatasvir (100 mg) and a potent, broad spectrum (pangenomic) HCV protease inhibitor, voxilaprevir (100 mg). This combination was approved for use in the United States in 2017 and is available under the brand name Vosevi. The recommended dosing regimen is 1 tablet daily for 12 weeks. This regimen is not recommended for patients with decompensated cirrhosis (Childs-Pugh Class B or C). As such, sofosbuvir

transformed the therapy of chronic hepatitis C and became the most commonly used HCV-specific antiviral agent, replacing peginterferon and combinations of peginterferon, ribavirin and protease inhibitors. Sofosbuvir has few side effects and in placebo controlled trials adverse events occurred at a similar rate with sofosbuvir as placebo. Side effects may include headache, dizziness, nausea and diarrhea. Rare, but potentially severe adverse events include marked bradycardia when sofosbuvir is given with amiodarone [6].

Structure Of Sofosbuvir [7]

CHROMATOGRAPHY

Chromatography is a technique which separates components in a mixture due to the differing time for each component to travel through stationary phase when carried through it by mobile phase.

The stationary phase is fixed in place either in column (a hollow tube made up of a suitable material e.g. Glass) or on a planar surface and the mobile phase moves over or through the stationary phase carrying with it the sample of interest. In practice the stationary phase can be a solid, a liquid adsorbed on a solid or an organic species bonded to a solid surface. In gas chromatography and supercritical fluid chromatography the stationary phase may be fixed in place either in a column or on a planar surface. In HPLC a column is used. The Name given to liquid chromatography on a planar surface is thin layer chromatography (TLC) [8,9].

Definition of Chromatography

In chromatography depending on how well each component dissolves in a pure solvent, they are transported individually, such as water or gas, as a pure solvent flows slowly over a stationary phase where the mixture has been separated. Greek words meaning "colour" and "to write" are the source of the word "chromatography" [10].

HIGH PERFORMANCE LIQUID CHROMATOGRAPHY

Figure No 1: Schematic diagram of HPLC instrumentation [11]

HPLC is one among most useful tools, available for quantitative analysis. Reverse phase chromatography refers to the use of a polar mobile phase with a nonpolar stationary phase in contrast, to normal phase being employed with a nonpolar mobile phase. Liquid chromatography is based upon the phenomenon that, under the same condition, each component in a mixture interacts with its environment differently from other components. Since HPLC is basically a separating technique, it is always used in conjunction with another analytical tool for quantitative and qualitative analysis. Advances in column technology, are high pressure pumping systems and sensitive detectors which have transformed liquid column chromatography into a high speed, high efficiency method of separation. This advanced technology is based upon the of small bore (2.5mm-internal diameter) columns and small particle size (3.5 micro meter) that allow fast equilibrium between stationary and mobile phases. This small particle column technology requires high pressure pumping system capable of delivering the mobile phase at high pressure, as much as 300 atmospheres to achieve flow rates of several ml per minutes. since it is often necessary to use small amounts of analyte with the column packing, sensitive detectors are needed. with this technology, liquid chromatography can give high speed separation when compared with many cases like those achieved by gas chromatography with the advantage that non-volatile or thermally unstable samples can be chromatographed without decomposition or the necessity for making volatile derivatives [11,12].

Principle of HPLC

A tiny volume of liquid sample is injected into a tube containing microscopic particles known as the stationary phase during the HPLC separation process. The sample components are subsequently

moved down the mobile phase by means of a pump into a densely packed tube or column. Chemical and physical interactions between the packing particles and components occur during column packing. An "HPLC" output is produced at the tube's exit when a detector counts the components that have been separated. Simpler liquid chromatography is still utilized for preliminary work, but HPLC offers faster processing times, more sensitivity, ease of use, and better speed [13].

REVERSE PHASE HIGH PERFORMANCE LIQUID CHROMATOGRAPHY

Reverse phase chromatography refers to the use of a polar eluants contrast to normal phase chromatography, where a polar stationary phase is employed with a phase chromatography is widely in use due to the following advantages. Many compound such as biologically active substances, have limited solubility in nonpolar solvents that are employed in normal phase chromatography. Ionic or highly polar compounds have high heats of adsorption on straight or alumina column and therefore can elute as a tailing peaks. Column deactivation from polar modifiers is a problem in liquid-solid chromatography, which frequently can lead to irreducibility in chromatography system. Ionic compound can be chromatographed via ion exchange chromatography. This mode of chromatography is tedious because precise control variable such as PH and ionic strength is required for reproducible chromatography [14].

MOBILE PHASE CHARACTERISTICS

Following points are considered for the selection of a mobile phase.

- Viscosity.
- Compressibility.
- Refractive index.
- UV cut off

- Polarity.
- Vapours pressure

The viscosity generally increases with the number of carbons in the solvent. Straight chain alcohol shows a very proposed relationship of this nature. For example, to achieve 1ml/min flow rate in a 4.6 x 250 mm column packed with 5 micro meter Octadecyl silane material, a pressure of 1500 psi is required with methanol. Solvent of low viscosity are needed to be compatible with the limitations of the pump. Also, as viscosity increases, the efficiency of the system, as measured by the number of theoretical plates decreases. The sensitivity of the detection is related to the difference between the refractive index, i.e. the greater the difference, greater is the sensitivity. The UV cut-off is defined as the wavelength below which the solvent will absorb more than 1.0 absorbance unit. The polarity of the solvent is a measure of the dielectric constant or the ability to elute particular types of compound. The vapour pressure of a solvent plays an important role in mobile phase selection. solvent reservoir could easily change in composition due to the evaporation of one of the more volatile constituents. The flammability of the mobile phase is a safety consideration. Careful attention should be paid to adequate ventilation and waste solvent disposition [15,16].

REVERSE MOBILE PHASE

The mobile phase in RP-HPLC, however, has a great influence on the solutes and the separation of component mixtures. The primary constituent of reverse phase-mobile phase is water. Water miscible solvent such as methanol, ethanol, Acetonitrile, dioxane tetrahydrofuran and DMF are added to adjust the polarity of the mobile phase. The water should be high quality, either distilled or demineralized. The most widely used organic modifier is methanol, Acetonitrile and

THF, methanol and Acetonitrile have comparable polarities but the latter is an aprotic solvent. This factor may be important if hydrogen bonding plays a significant role in the separation. When inorganic salt and ionic surfactants are used the mobile phase are generally non inflammable due to high water content degassing is quite or important with reverse phase mobile phases [17,18].

NORMAL PHASE

Normal phase chromatography was one of the earliest forms of liquid chromatography. It employs a polar stationary phase (most commonly silica gel) and a non-polar or low-polarity mobile phase (e.g., hexane, chloroform, ethyl acetate). In this setup, analytes with stronger polarity interact more intensely with the stationary phase, resulting in longer retention times and delayed elution [19,20].

EXPERIMENTAL WORK

Preparation of standard stock solutions

In order to prepare stock solution, weighed accurately 20 mg Sofosbuvir and transferred into 20 ml volumetric flask, added 15 ml of Methanol and sonicated to dissolve the standard completely and diluted up to the mark with Methanol (1000 PPM). Further diluted 0.5 mL to 25 mL with methanol. (20 PPM)

Preparation of standard stock solution for Chromatographic development:

Sofosbuvir Standard stock solution was prepared by transferring 10 mg Sofosbuvir into a 20 mL clean and dried volumetric flask, added about 15 mL of Methanol to dissolve it completely and made volume up to the mark with methanol. (500 PPM).

Further diluted 2 ml of stock solution to 10 mL with mobile phase (100 PPM). It was prepared in

mobile phase of each trial and injected in development trials.

Validation of RP-HPLC Method

FILTRATION STUDY:

Filtration study of an analytical procedure checks the interference of extraneous components from filter, deposition on filter bed and compatibility of filter with sample.

This study was conducted with Sofosbuvir Test sample (Tablet solution).

Filtration study carried out with unfiltered and filtered test solution. During filtration activity 0.45 µm PVDF and 0.45 µm Nylon syringe filters used by discarding 5 mL of aliquot sample.

SPECIFICITY:

Specificity is the ability to access unequivocally the analyte in the presence of components which may be expected to be present.

Following solution shall be prepared and injected to prove the specificity nature of the method.

1. Blank (Mobile phase as Blank)
2. Placebo

Analyzing marketed test sample contains excipients (additives) which are totally unknown. So Placebo prepared at lab level by using formula as follows:

Placebo preparation:

Sr. No.	Ingredients	Role	Qty (mg)
1	Lactose	Filler	80
2	Starch	Binder	5
3	Magnesium stearate	Lubricant	5
4	Talc	Glidant	5
5	Crospovidone	Disintegrants	5
Total			100 mg

Total 10 gm of placebo prepared.

Placebo Solution Preparation:

Weighed 22.10 mg of placebo material (Which is equivalent to 50 mg of Sofosbuvir) and transferred to clean and dried 100 mL of volumetric flask. Added 70 mL of Methanol, sonicate for 10 minutes with intermittent shaking. After 10 minutes allow to cool the solution to room temperature and made volume up to the mark with Methanol. Filtered the solution through suitable 0.45 µ Nylon syringe filter discarding 3-5 mL of initial filtrate. Further dilute 1.0 ml of filtered stock solution to 25 ml with mobile phase, injected the resultant solution and chromatograms were recorded.

LINEARITY AND RANGE

Preparation of linearity solution

The linearity of an analytical procedure is its ability (within a given range) to obtain test results which are directly proportional to the concentration (amount) of analyte in the sample.

5 levels of Linearity was performed from 50% to 150% of working concentration

Linearity Sofosbuvir stock solution:

Weighed 25 mg of Sofosbuvir and dissolved in 25 mL with Methanol. Further diluted 5 ml of stock solution to 50 mL with Methanol (100 µg/mL)

Linearity levels prepared as follows:

Sr. No.	Level (%)	mL of stock solution	Diluted to with Mobile phase (mL)	Sofosbuvir Concentration (µg/mL)
1	50	2.00	20	10.0
2	75	3.00	20	15.0
3	100	4.00	20	20.0
4	125	5.00	20	25.0
5	150	6.00	20	30.0

ACCURACY (% RECOVERY)

The accuracy of the analytical procedure expresses the closeness of agreement between the value

which is accepted either as a conventional true value or an accepted reference value and the value of the value found,

Accuracy will be conducted in the range from 50 % to 150 % of working concentration. Solution of each accuracy level was prepared in triplicate. Calculated % Recovery for each sample, Mean % recovery for each level and overall recovery and also calculated % RSD for each level and % RSD for overall recovery.

Accuracy levels details:

Refer Following table for each sample:

Level (%)	API (mg)	Placebo	Diluted to (mL)	Volume taken (mL)	Diluted to (mL)	Conc (µg/mL)
50	25.3	22.6	100	1	25	10.12
	25.1	21.7	100	1	25	10.04
	25.2	21.9	100	1	25	10.08
100	50.1	22.3	100	1	25	20.04
	50.2	22.1	100	1	25	20.08
	50.0	21.9	100	1	25	20.00
150	75.2	22.5	100	1	25	30.08
	75.1	21.6	100	1	25	30.04
	75.3	22.3	100	1	25	30.12

Procedure for preparation of Accuracy sample solution:

Take clean and dried 9 volumetric flasks of 100 mL. Weighed approx 22.10 mg of placebo and transferred in each 100 mL volumetric flask. Weighed Sofosbuvir API as per accuracy level and transferred in same 100 ml volumetric flask. Add 70 ml of Methanol sonicate it for 10 minutes with intermittent shaking. Allowed to cool the solution at room temperature and made the volume up to the mark with Methanol. Filter the solution through suitable 0.45 µ Nylon filter discarding 5 mL of filtrate. Further dilute 1.0 ml of filtrate to 25 ml with mobile phase.

1. % Recovery for each sample and Mean recovery and overall recovery should be in the range of 98-102%.
2. The Relative Standard Deviation should not be more than 2.0%.

PRECISION

Precision of an analytical procedure expresses the closeness of agreement between a series of measurements obtained from multiple sampling of the same homogeneous test under the prescribed conditions. Precision is of two types, Repeatability and Intermediate precision. It is performed on tablet test sample.

I. Repeatability:

Acceptance criteria

Preparation of sample solution (6 Samples prepared):

Weighed 20 tablets transferred in mortar pestle and crushed to fine powder. Mixed the contents with butter paper uniformly. Weighed the powder material equivalent to 50 mg of Sofosbuvir (72.10 mg of powder material) and transferred to clean and dried 100 mL of volumetric flask. Added 70 mL of Methanol, sonicated for 10 minutes with intermittent shaking. After 10 minutes allow to cool the solution to room temperature and made

volume up to the mark with Methanol. Filtered the solution through suitable 0.45 μ Nylon syringe filter discarding 3-5 mL of initial filtrate. Further diluted 1.0 ml of filtered stock solution to 25 ml with mobile phase. (20 mcg of Sofosbuvir), injected the resultant solution and chromatograms were recorded.

Six samples prepared.

Precision (Repeatability) Sample details are as follows:

Sample	Powder wt (mg)	Diluted to (mL)	Volume taken (mL)	Diluted to (mL)
Sample 1	72.6	100	1	25
Sample 2	72.3	100	1	25
Sample 3	71.5	100	1	25
Sample 4	72.5	100	1	25
Sample 5	71.8	100	1	25
Sample 6	71.7	100	1	25

Acceptance criteria:

% Assay: 90-110% for each sample and mean assay value

% RSD for % assay value of 6 samples: NMT 2%

I. Intermediate precision

It is performed by doing analysis on another day to check reproducibility of results. Samples prepared in same manner as that of Repeatability parameter (6 Samples prepared).

Intermediate Precision Sample details are as follows:

Sample	Powder wt. (mg)	Diluted to (mL)	Volume taken (mL)	Diluted to (mL)
Sample 1	71.8	100	1	25
Sample 2	72.4	100	1	25
Sample 3	71.6	100	1	25
Sample 4	72.7	100	1	25
Sample 5	72.2	100	1	25
Sample 6	72.4	100	1	25

Acceptance criteria:

% Assay: 90-110% for each sample and mean assay value

% RSD for % assay of 6 samples of Intermediate precision: NMT 2

% RSD for Total 12 samples: NMT 2% for test results (6 of Repeatability and 6 of Intermediate precision)

Limit of Detection (LOD) and Limit of Quantitation (LOQ)

Detection limit:

The detection limit of an individual analytical procedure is the lowest amount of analyte in a sample which can be detected but not necessarily quantitated as an exact value.

Quantitation limit:

The quantitation limit of an individual analytical procedure is the lowest amount of analyte in a sample which can be quantitatively determined with suitable precision and accuracy.

As per ICH Q2R1 guidelines LOD and LOQ was determined by using the approach Based on the Calibration Curve in which residual standard deviation of a regression line was calculated and determined the LOD and LOQ by using following formula:

$$LOD = 3.3 \sigma / S$$

$$LOQ = 10 \sigma / S$$

Where,

σ = residual standard deviation of a regression line

S = Slope of regression line

ROBUSTNESS

The robustness of an analytical procedure is a measure of its capacity to remain unaffected by small, but deliberate variations in method parameters and provides an indication of its reliability during normal usage.

Determination: Standard solution was injected under different chromatographic conditions as shown below.

- a) Changes in flow rate by $\pm 10\%$. (± 0.1 ml/min)
- b) Change in column oven temperature. ($\pm 2^\circ\text{C}$)
- c) Change in wavelength (± 3 nm)

RESULT AND DISCUSSION

FILTRATION STUDY:

Filtration study of an analytical procedure checks the interference of extraneous components from filter, deposition on filter bed and compatibility of filter with sample. Performed on tablet test sample.

Results of Filter study

Sample description	Area	% Absolute difference
Unfiltered	7410625	NA
0.45 μ PVDF filter	7340256	0.95
0.45 μ Nylon filter	7365014	0.62

Chromatograms:

Fig. No. 8 Typical chromatogram of unfiltered sample.

Fig. No. 9 Typical chromatogram of sample filtered through 0.45µ PVDF filter.

Fig. No. 10 Typical chromatogram of sample filtered through 0.45µ Nylon filter.

Acceptance criteria: % Absolute difference of filtered samples NMT 2.0 w.r.t. Unfiltered sample.

Data interpretation: Both filters PVDF and Nylon passes the criteria for filter study, hence both filters can be used. We used Nylon filter because it showed less absolute difference as compare to PVDF filter.

SPECIFICITY:

Specificity is the ability to access unequivocally the analyte in the presence of components which may be expected to be present.

Blank and Placebo solution prepared and injected to check interference at R.T of Sofosbuvir.

Results of Specificity.

Description	Observation
Blank	No interference at R.T. of Sofosbuvir due to blank
Placebo	No interference at R.T. of Sofosbuvir due to placebo

Chromatograms:

Fig. No. 15 Typical chromatogram of Blank solution.

Fig. No. 16 Typical chromatogram of Placebo solution.

Acceptance criteria:

- **Blank:** There should be no Interference at R.T. of Sofosbuvir
- **Placebo:** There should be no Interference at R.T. of Sofosbuvir

Linearity and Range

Linearity of an analytical method is its ability to elicit test results that are proportional to the concentration of analyte in samples within a given range.

Data interpretation: Blank and placebo was not having interference at R.T. of Sofosbuvir. Hence developed chromatographic method passed the criteria for specificity.

Linearity Data for Sofosbuvir:

Level	Conc (µg/mL)	Area	Mean	% RSD
50%	10.00	3718317	3721209	0.160
		3717256		
		3728053		
75%	15.00	5566419	5558281	0.157
		5549102		

		5559321		
100%	20.00	7432282	7429221	0.179
		7440691		
		7414690		
125%	25.00	9226566	9227047	0.170
		9211569		
		9243005		
150%	30.00	11128821	11151454	0.184
		11156536		
		11169004		

Fig. No. 17 Calibration curve of Sofosbuvir.

Data of linearity of Sofosbuvir:

Sr no.	Parameter	Result value	Acceptance criteria
1	Beer's linearity range	10.0-30.0 µg/mL	NA
2	Correlation coefficient (R ²)	0.99996	NLT 0.98
3	Intercept	5740	To be report
4	Slope	370585.12	To be report
5	% RSD for area at each level	NA	NMT 2.0

The respective linear equation for Sofosbuvir was: $Y = \text{is area of peak.}$

$Y = M X + C$ $M = \text{Slope}$

$Y = 370585.12 X + 5740$ $C = \text{Intercept}$

Where, X = concentration of Analyte in µg/mL **Chromatograms:**

Sample Name: LINEARITY 50%_1

VWD: Signal
A, 261 nm

Results Name	Retention Time	Area	Asymmetry	Theoretical plates (USP)
Sofosbuvir	3.12	3718317	1.24	10354
Totals		3718317		

Fig. No. 18 Typical chromatogram of Linearity 50%.

Sample Name: LINEARITY 75%_1

VWD: Signal
A, 261 nm

Results Name	Retention Time	Area	Asymmetry	Theoretical plates (USP)
Sofosbuvir	3.12	5566419	1.26	9846
Totals		5566419		

Fig. No. 19 Typical chromatogram of Linearity 75%.

Sample Name: LINEARITY 100%_1

VWD: Signal
A, 261 nm

Results Name	Retention Time	Area	Asymmetry	Theoretical plates (USP)
Sofosbuvir	3.13	7432282	1.21	8928
Totals		7432282		

Fig. No. 20 Typical chromatogram of Linearity 100%.

Sample Name: LINEARITY 125%_1

VWD: Signal
A, 261 nm

Results Name	Retention Time	Area	Asymmetry	Theoretical Plates (USP)
Sofosbuvir	3.14	9226566	1.23	7851
Totals		9226566		

Fig. No. 21 Typical chromatogram of Linearity 125%.

Sample Name: LINEARITY 150%_1

VWD: Signal
A, 261 nm

Results Name	Retention Time	Area	Asymmetry	Theoretical plates (USP)
Sofosbuvir	3.14	11128821	1.18	7083
Totals		11128821		

Fig. No. 22 Typical chromatogram of Linearity 150%.

Conclusion:

From the calibration curve it was concluded that the Sofosbuvir shows linear response in the range of 10.0-30.0 µg /ml. The Regression value was found well within the limit.

The accuracy of an analytical method is the closeness of test results obtained by that method to the true value. The accuracy of an analytical method is determined by applying the method to analyzed samples to which known amounts of analyte have been added.

ACCURACY (RECOVERY):

Result and statistical data of Accuracy of Sofosbuvir

Level (%)	Area	Recovered conc (µg/mL)	Added conc (µg/mL)	% Recovery	Mean Recovery	% RSD
50	3721025	10.00	10.12	98.81	99.61	1.0568
	3764812	10.12	10.04	100.80		
	3721004	10.00	10.08	99.21		
100	7479851	20.10	20.04	100.30	99.58	0.7035
	7389586	19.86	20.08	98.90		

	7410509	19.91	20.00	99.55		
150	11124104	29.89	30.08	99.37	99.82	1.0892
	11069140	29.75	30.04	99.03		
	11326925	30.44	30.12	101.06		

Overall Recovery: 99.67 %

Chromatograms:

% RSD for Overall Recovery: 0.844

Sample Name: ACCURACY 50%_1

VWD: Signal

A, 261 nm

Results

Name

Retention Time

Area

Asymmetry

Theoretical

Plates (USP)

Sofosbuvir

3.13

3721025

1.23

10304

Totals

3721025

Fig. No. 23 Typical chromatogram of Accuracy 50%.

Sample Name: ACCURACY 100%_1

VWD: Signal

A, 261 nm

Results

Name

Retention Time

Area

Asymmetry

Theoretical

Plates (USP)

Sofosbuvir

3.13

7479851

1.22

8990

Totals

7479851

Fig. No. 24 Typical chromatogram of Accuracy 100%.

Sample Name: ACCURACY 150%_1

VWD: Signal
A, 261 nm

Results Name	Retention Time	Area	Asymmetry	Theoretical Plates (USP)
Sofosbuvir	3.14	11124104	1.17	7023
Totals		11124104		

Fig. No. 25 Typical chromatogram of Accuracy 150%.

Acceptance criteria:

% Recovery for each level and overall recovery:
98.0 to 102.0%

% RSD for each level and overall recovery: NMT
2.0

Data interpretation: Recovery of analytical procedure was found well within acceptance criteria at all 3 levels. % Recovery not get hampered by changed in analyte concentration.

PRECISION

Precision of an analytical method is the degree of agreement among individual test results when the procedure is applied repeatedly to multiple samplings of a homogenous sample. Precision of an analytical method is usually expressed as standard deviation or relative standard deviation. Precision was performed on Test sample.

Result of Intra- day and Inter- Day Precision for Sofosbuvir test sample assay:

Repeatability	Sample	Test Sample (mg)	Area	% Assay
	Sample 1	72.6	7326025	97.76
	Sample 2	72.3	7392510	99.05
	Sample 3	71.5	7456991	101.04
	Sample 4	72.5	7360460	98.35
	Sample 5	71.8	7416942	100.07
	Sample 6	71.7	7321525	98.92
	Mean			
STD DEV				1.186548
% RSD				1.196
Intermediate precision (Inter-Day)	Sample 1	71.8	7362514	99.34
	Sample 2	72.4	7312804	97.85
	Sample 3	71.6	7439170	100.65
	Sample 4	72.7	7414196	98.80
	Sample 5	72.2	7236521	97.10
	Sample 6	72.4	7429140	99.41
	Mean			

Repeatability Plus Inter-day	STD DEV	1.253657
	% RSD	1.268
	Mean	99.028
	STD DEV	1.17723
	% RSD	1.189

Chromatograms:

Fig. No. 26 Typical chromatogram of Repeatability precision (Sample 1).

Fig. No. 27 Typical chromatogram of Inter-day precision (Sample 1).

Acceptance criteria:

% Assay: % Assay value for each sample (Individual sample) and mean assay value for precision (6 sample), mean assay value intermediate precision (6 sample), and mean assay

value for precision plus intermediate precision sample (12 sample): 90-110%

% RSD: : % RSD for precision study samples(6 sample), Intermediate precision study samples (6 sample) and precision plus intermediate precision sample (12 sample): NMT 2.0

Data interpretation: % Assay and % RSD was found well within acceptance limit and hence method is precise (Reproducible).

$$LOQ = 10 \sigma / S$$

$$LOQ = 10 \times 27110.14508 / 370585.12$$

Limit of Detection (LOD) and Limit of Quantitation (LOQ)

$$LOQ = 0.732 \mu\text{g/mL}$$

$\sigma = 27110.14508$ (Residual standard deviation of a regression line)

$s = 370585.12$ (Slope)

Detection limit (LOD):

$$LOD = 3.3 \sigma / S$$

$$LOD = 3.3 \times 27110.14508 / 370585.12$$

$$LOD = 0.241 \mu\text{g/mL}$$

Quantitation limit (LOQ):

ROBUSTNESS

The robustness of an analytical method is a measure of its capacity to remain unaffected by small but deliberate variations in method parameters and provides an indication of its reliability during normal usage.

Following changes made under Robustness:

- Change in Wavelength
- Change in flow rate
- Change in column oven temperature

Tab.No.30 Result of Robustness study:

Change in Parameter	R.T.	Standard area	Asymmetry	Theoretical plates
Wavelength by +3 NM (264 NM)	3.14	7203093	1.24	8945
Wavelength by -3 NM (258 NM)	3.14	7360164	1.21	8942
Flow rate by +10% (1.1mL/min)	2.85	6766525	1.23	8430
Flow rate by -10% (0.9mL/min)	3.49	8272895	1.26	9488
Column oven temp by +2°C (42 °C)	3.12	7386195	1.24	9127
Column oven temp by -2°C (38 °C)	3.13	7404958	1.22	9014

Chromatograms:

A. Change in Wavelength by +3 NM:

Fig. No. 29 Typical chromatogram of Standard +3 NM.

B. Change in Wavelength by -3 NM:

Fig. No. 30 Typical chromatogram of Standard -3 NM.

C. Change in Flow rate by + 10% (1.1 mL/min)

Fig. No. 31 Typical chromatogram of Standard +10 F.R.%.

D. Change in Flow rate by - 10% (0.9 mL/min)

Fig. No. 32 Typical chromatogram of Standard -10 F.R.%.

E. Change in Column Oven temperature by +2°C:

Fig. No. 33 Typical chromatogram of Standard +2°C C.O.T.

F. Change in Column Oven temperature by -2°C:

Fig. No. 34 Typical chromatogram of Standard -2°C C.O.T.

Acceptance criteria:

Chromatography (System suitability) acceptance criteria should not get failed.

Data interpretation: From the above results, it was concluded that the system suitability test

result was found well within the limits and analytical method was robust.

CONCLUSION

The Validated Chromatographic Strategy was found to be accurate, simple, and decisive for the quantitative estimation of Ledipasvir and

Sofosbuvir in bulk and fixed dosage form. Different trials were carried out to determine the optimized chromatographic conditions, and an initial attempt was performed by utilizing a low proportion of organic solvents for the elution of compounds by reducing the retention time of the compounds, which made the strategy economical. The proposed method is easy, speedy, and measurably substantial. During the drug analysis, no interfering peak was found within the chromatogram, indicating that there is no excipient interference. Hence this method can be employed for routine quality control analysis of Ledipasvir and Sofosbuvir samples.

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